

ANALYSIS OF INDIVIDUAL ATHLETES WHO HAVE RETURNED REPUTABLE RESULTS FROM FIGURE FLYING SPORTS

Nurmamatova Sarvinoz Kurbon's daughter

*Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports
Theory and methodology of winter and complex technical sports*

Uzbekistan, Chirchik

nurmamatovasarvinoz0103@gmail.com

Davletov Siyovush Khushvaqt's son

*Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports
Theory and methodology of winter and complex technical sports*

Uzbekistan, Chirchik

Annotation: In this article, the major achievements and lower results in the sports careers of Misha Ge and Ilia Malinin are analyzed.

Key words: Misha Ge, Ilia Malinin, Uzbekistan Championship, Skate Canada, Winter Olympic Games, figure skating, sports achievements.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Misha Ge va Ilia Malinning sport faoliyatidagi eng yirik yutuqlari va past ko'rsatkichlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Misha Ge, Ilia Malinin, O'zbekiston chempionati, Skate Canada, Qishki Olimpiya o'yinlari, figurali uchish, sport yutuqlari.

Абстракт: В данной статье анализируются крупнейшие достижения и низкие результаты в спортивной карьере Миши Ге и Ильи Малнина.

Ключевые слова: Misha Ge, Ilia Malinin, чемпионат Узбекистана, Skate Canada, зимние Олимпийские игры, фигурное катание, спортивные достижения.

Introduction: Ilia Malinin was born on December 2, 2003 in Arlington, Virginia. Malinin's acquaintance with ice skating began in childhood. He was interested in sports from a young age, took his first steps on the local ice rinks. His father, in turn, was a person interested in music, which was a source of inspiration for Ilia. Throughout his many training sessions, Ilia strived to succeed with his father's motivation and support.

At a very young age, he faced a major injury, which hindered his career. But these difficulties made him stronger. He continued to prepare to regain his health and prove himself once again. Malinin's flying style is a combination of technical skills and creative expression. It combines complex jump sequences with modern step movements and emotional choreography to give the audience a captivating performance. Personal life Malinin attracts attention with his personal life in addition to his sports activities. He also devotes time to his hobbies, such as listening to music and learning about his interests. Spending time with family and friends gives him motivation and reduces stress. He attributes his success in sports to his family and coaches, who constantly support him.

Misha Ge, full name Misha Aloyzievich Ge, was born on May 17, 1991 in Moscow, Russia. His parents are figure skating coaches, and Misha started skating at an early age due to his interest in sports. From the age of 4, Misha began to learn the art of ice skating, which allowed him to perfectly combine

dance and technique at the same time. Family members, especially her mother, Larisa Ge, spent time with her and conducted programs and exercises aimed at creating perfect figures. Misha's coaching style is multifaceted, he teaches young athletes not only the technique of figure skating, but also how to express emotions on stage. In addition to sports, Misha loves music and literature, and this has a positive effect on his creative processes.

Table -3

Analysis of achievements of Ilia Malin in figure skating during his sports career

MUSOBAQALARDAGI ISHTIROKI	Competition	Ilya Malinin	Year	Competition	Misha GE	Year
	Winter Olympic Games	4-position	2022	Winter Olympic Games	17 position	2013-2014
	World championships	2-position	2023	World championships	6 position	2014-2015
	Four continental championships	3-position	2023	Four continental championships	6 position	2017-2018
	Grand prix rounds			Grand Prix: China Cup	5 position	2014-2015
	Xitoy Kubogi	1-position	2023	Grand-pri: Rostelekom Cup	4 position	2014-2015
	Rostelecom Cup	1-position	2022	Grand-pri: Skate Canada	6 position	2016-2017
	Skate Canada	1-position	2022	Grand-pri:Trophée de France	3 position	2017-2018
	Trophée de France	1-position	2022	Uzbekistan championships	1 position	2009-2010
	Uzbekistan championships	1-position	2023	Asian Winter Games	6 position	2010-2011
	Asian Winter Games	1-position	2023	Osiyo trofey	2 position	2010-2011
	Asian trophy	1-position	2023	Finlandiya trofeyi	4 position	2014-2015
	Finnish trophy	2-position	2022	Warsaw Cup	2 position	2012-2013
	Warsaw Cup	1-position	2023	Autumn classics international competition	2 position	2016-2017
	Autumn classics international competition	1-position	2023	NRW trophy	5 position	2012-2013
	NRW trophy	1-position	2023	Nice International Cup	8 position	2011-2012
Nice International Cup	1-position	2023	Icechallenge	2 position	2011-2012	

Note: Comparison of the total results of the two biggest athletes of Uzbekistan who recorded the highest sports results.

A summary of all the major achievements of Ilia Malinin and Misha Ge during their sports career in figure skating. In 2010, Misha Ge achieved his biggest achievement in the championship of Uzbekistan and took the 1st place. He

recorded his lowest performance at the 2014 Winter Olympics, taking 17th place. Ilia Malinin achieved his biggest achievement at Skate Canada in 2022, taking 1st place. He recorded his lowest performance at the 2022 Winter Olympics by taking 4th place.

In conclusion, we can note that when Misha Ge and Ilia Malinin are compared in terms of figure skating successes and failures, the achievements of both athletes are unique and impressive, and their contributions to figure skating are significant. is important. Misha Ge participated in a number of international competitions on behalf of Uzbekistan and in 2010 won the 1st place in the championship of Uzbekistan. However, his 17th place finish at the Sochi 2014 Olympics is remembered as his lowest performance. Ilia Malinin, one of the athletes shaping the future of figure skating with her creative and technical approach, won the 1st place at Skate Canada in 2022. Malinin's lowest performance is 4th place at the 2022 Winter Olympics. Both athletes' unique abilities, strong mental state and dedication to the sport have led them to take their place in the world of figure skating. Their achievements have received great recognition on the global scale of the sport, increasing the likelihood of achieving even greater success in the future.

ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI

1. Davletmuratov S. R. "Comparative analysis of the endangerment under the criminal law of some developed foreign countries." *Review of law sciences* 3.1 (2018): 21.

2. Fedorova Svetlana Vyacheslavovna "Fundamentals of selection in figure skating." *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies* 2.11 (2022): 327-331.

3. Karimov Abdukhamid Abdumannabovich "Studying the state of physical and technical fitness of young hockey players under the age 12-14." *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies* 2.12 (2022): 292-298.

4. Nurmamatova, Sarvinoz. "Development of coordination skills in figure skating." *Академические исследования в современной науке* 2.11 (2023): 107-110.

5. Sarvinoz, Nurmamatova. "ANALYSIS OF UZBEK ATHLETES WHO HAVE ACHIEVED PRESTIGIOUS RESULTS IN FIGURE SKATING." *PEDAGOGS* 69.2 (2024): 35-40.